

Interesting behaviour of two wolf spiders *Hogna spenceri* and *H. transvaalica* in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: Chelicerae flashing, an interesting behaviour observed in the wolf spiders *Hogna spenceri* (Pocock, 1898) and *H. transvaalica* (Simon, 1898), is discussed. Both species are African endemics. The general morphology of the species is discussed and photographs of live specimens are provided showing how the chelicerae colour changes. Notes on their lifestyle, distribution and conservation status are provided.

Key words: Afrotropical Region, burrow dwellers, chelicerae flashing, defense mechanism, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

A large number of Lycosidae were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Presently, 24 Lycosidae genera represented by 110 species are known from South Africa. Since the use of pitfall trap in terrestrial invertebrate surveys, the number of lycosids in spider collections has increased dramatically. Although large numbers of specimens have been collected, little is still known about specific generic and species behaviour.

Some of the larger lycosids belong to the genus *Hogna* Simon, 1885. This large genus is represented by 234 species (World Spider Catalog, 2022) and presently 13 species are recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). In this paper we provide more information on the general morphology of *Hogna spenceri* (Pocock, 1898) and *H. transvaalica* (Simon, 1898) with notes on their lifestyle, some interesting defense mechanisms, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria. As part of SANSa, requests were made for photographs of spiders for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) and several sets of photographs of *Hogna* spp. have been received from the public.

TAXONOMIC NOTES

Members of *Hogna* belong to the subfamily Lycosinae. This subfamily is still poorly known and one of the most diverse in the Afrotropical region. The 13 species recorded from South Africa have not yet been revised. *H. spenceri* and *H. transvaalica* are two species that have been sampled with pitfall traps during several SANSa surveys in the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011, Haddad *et al.*, 2013). Series of photographs were received from seven localities.

Both species are large spiders (22 mm) and have the typical *Hogna* eye pattern, with the width of the bottom row of eyes less than the width of the two largest eyes in the middle row (Fig. 3). They occur sympatric and are recorded from seven of the nine South African provinces. The two species resemble each other, with only the dorsal abdominal pattern (Figs 1, 2) and ventrum (Figs 5 & 14) that differ as well as the genitalia. In both species the setae on the chelicerae change colour when the carapace is tilted backwards. The chelicerae are normally the same colour as the carapace (Fig. 1), but when the carapace is tilted backwards, the setae on the chelicerae change colour (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. *Hogna spenceri* female dorsal view Photo: Peter Webb

Figure 2. *Hogna transvaalica* female dorsal view. Photo: Peter Webb

Figure 3. *Hogna transvaalica* female showing the eye pattern Photo: Peter Webb

Figures 4–5. *Hogna spenceri* female: 3. Dorsal view. 4. Ventral view. Photo credits: Peter Webb

Hogna spenceri (Pocock, 1898)

Lycosa spenceri Pocock, 1898: 313; Lessert, 1915: 60.

Hogna spenceri Roewer, 1955: 251; Roewer, 1959: 463; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 67.

Diagnostic characteristics: Cephalothorax fawn with two lateral dark bands and narrow marginal dark band. Eye field fawn. Abdomen dorsally fawn with blackish inverted V-shaped dark marking anteriorly; mark bordered by broad fawn bands (Figs 4 & 6); markings extend posteriorly in series of dark chevrons. Ventral abdomen, as well as sternum and coxae, deep black, remaining leg links pale yellow, unspotted; chelicerae dark brown, lightly hairy frontal. Total length 22 mm (Roewer 1960).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Hogna spenceri is an African endemic described by Pocock (1898) as *Lycosa spenceri* from Durban. The species is also known from Rwanda and Swaziland.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Free State: Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Bronkhorstspuit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74; 28.19); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.87, 28.22); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Estcourt (-29.00, 29.87); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); iSimangaliso Wetland park uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.62, 32.25). **Limpopo:** Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Molle Molle (-24.65, 28.67); Vhembe Biosphere Ben Lavin Nature Reserve (-23.13, 29.93); Vhembe Biosphere Mara Research Station (-23.12, 29.55); Vhembe Biosphere Mashovelo Lodge (-22.94, 29.88); Western Soutpansberg (-22.95, 29.87); Ellisras/Lephalale (-27.71, 23.32). **Mpumalanga:** Carolina Farm Nooitgedacht (-26.06, 30.11). **North West:** Wolmaransstad (-27.19, 25.97). **North-ern Cape:** Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.561, 24.162).

Hogna transvaalica known distribution

Figure 6–10. *Hogna spenceri*: 6. Female line drawing after Roewer, (1959). 7. Palp. 8–9. Palp and epigyne line drawing after Roewer (1959). 10. Epigyne.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

There are no significant threats to the species and it is protected in six protected areas: Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide geographical range, it is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

Hogna transvaalica (Simon, 1898)

Lycosa transvaalica Simon, 1898. *Hogna transvaalica* Roewer, 1955: 252; Roewer, 1959: 468; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 68.

Diagnostic characteristics: Cephalothorax fawn to grey with two dark brown lateral bands and narrow marginal dark lateral bands with three pale striae on both sides. Eye field fawn. Abdomen dorsally fawn with broad median band consisting of marking anteriorly; mark bordered by broad fawn bands (Figs 11 & 12); markings extend posteriorly in series of dark chevrons. Ventral abdomen, as well as sternum and coxae, deep black, but decorated by six white spots (Fig. 13 & 14); two on epigastric areas and four on remaining area. Legs pale yellow to grey, unspotted. Total length 20 mm

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

A Southern African endemic described by Simon (1898) as *Lycosa transvaalica* with type locality given only as “Africa australis Bechuanaland, Griqualand W., Transvaal”. Presently reported from South Africa and Botswana.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

There are no significant threats to the species and it is protected in 11 protected areas: Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler, 2018); Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 2003; Robertson *et al.* 2011). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide geographical range, it is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

Figures 11–15. *Hogna transvaalica* female: 11. Female (Photo: Peter Webb). 12.–13. Female habitus dorsal and ventral view after Roewer (1959). 14. Abdomen ventral view (Photo: Peter Webb). 15. Epigyne after Roewer (1959).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Tsolwana Nature Reserve (-32.171, 26.5). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77); National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Wolfkop (-29.08, 26.04); Naval Hill, Hangmanskloof (-29.06, 26.14); Oliewenhuis Art Museum, Grant's Hill (-29.06, 26.13); Schoemansdrif (-26.58, 27.13); Bloemfontein (-29.08, 26.10); Tussen die Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.29, 26.07). **Gauteng:** Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74; 28.19); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.87, 28.22); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **Limpopo:** Makapansgat (-24.15, 29.18); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lephahlale Nature Reserve (-23.67, 27.71).

Mpumalanga: Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58); Kruger National Park: Skukuza (-25.00, 31.97); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46). **Northern Cape:** Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.56, 24.16); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.3, 22.44); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82).

BEHAVIOUR

Hogna species are known to live in open burrows. While photographing them it was observed that in some species the colour of the setae on the chelicerae change in colour from fawn (Fig. 16) to a signal red (Fig 21) when the carapace is tilted. The chelicerae are normally the same colour as the carapace, but when in danger they tilt the carapace backwards and the setae on the chelicerae become a flaming orange-red colour (Figs 16–22). This probably acts as a warning to enemies.

The colour change of the chelicerae was also seen in the males. In Figs 23–24 the red setae on the old exuviae of a male *H. transvaalica* can be seen.

Some of the other *Hogna* species photographed that do not show any cheliceral colour change include *H. adjacens* Roewer, 1959; *H. lawrencei* (Roewer, 1960); *H. simoni* Roewer, 1959 and *H. zuluana* Roewer, 1959.

Figures 16–21. *Hogna* spp. showing how the chelicerae change in colour. 16–19. *H. spenceri*. 20–22. *H. transvaalica*. Photo credit: Peter Webb

Figures 23–24. *Hogna transvaalica* male exuviae showing the coloured setae on the chelicerae.

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